

Mapping Winter Fallow Fields for Biogas Production: A Semantic Data Cube Approach to Enhance Cover Crop Potential in Austria

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In pursuit of fulfilling the upcoming NetZero goals, energy production is transitioning from fossil fuels to renewable sources. Achieving this transformation requires a diverse mix of renewable energy options. Biogas generation from biomass, in particular, has the potential to play a significant role in the future of renewable energy production. Biogas plants use agricultural by-products such as straw and maize stalks, animal manure, food waste and also energy crops (e.g. maize, sorghum). Energy crops have the advantage of a high biomass yield, but they compete with food production. In Austria, the use of such feedstocks is strictly limited. One idea to compensate for this disadvantage is to plant cover crops during the winter season or when the main crop has been harvested and the field is left fallow. For the planning of potential sites for future biogas plants, it would be very valuable to know where there are more fallow fields in winter. The use of Earth Observation (EO) data to identify these areas provides a cost- and time-efficient solution. However, analysing fields and vegetation patterns in winter months can be challenging and is not often done due to persistent snow and cloud cover. We try to overcome limitations of available data by the use of an approach implemented within a semantic data cube environment to identify fallow fields successfully.

To identify untapped potential for cover crops, we analysed the vegetation pattern on agricultural land from September to April in three different regions of Austria (Innviertel, Mostviertel, Südburgenland) from 2018 to 2023. For this purpose, we employed a semantic analysis approach using the Sen2Cube.at semantic EO data cube. The Sen2Cube.at system contains all semantically enriched Sentinel-2 images captured of Austria and provides cloud-based analysis tools (Sudmanns et al., 2021). To obtain the field polygons, we used the INVEKOS (Integrated Administration and Control System) open data (Agrarmarkt Austria, n.d.), which field pieces and crop types recorded by the applicants, which serve as the basis for funding processing. We first filtered the INVEKOS data to include only fields that are neither too small, nor have a main crop planted in winter (e.g. winter maize, fruit trees, grassland). A small field exists if, after subtracting a buffer of half the geometrical standard derivation (to compensate for geometric inaccuracies) along the boundaries of an agricultural area, more than 60% of the pixels that were originally within the area are now partially outside it. We then extracted time series information of each field using semantic analysis within Sen2Cube.at. The advantage of the semantic analysis is that each pixel has a category assigned derived from the pixel's spectral signature (e.g. cloud, barren land or built-up, water or shadow, etc.). This allows efficient and comprehensive time series analysis at the pixel level (increasing the amount of usable data compared to cloud filtering on image wide statistics), which can be aggregated over the agricultural fields. As a result, we obtained a time series of percentage of bare soil, weak, medium and strong vegetation, clouds, snow and shadow per field. From this, we developed an algorithm in R to categorise the fields according to their vegetation patterns per season (autumn, winter, spring) to identify fallow fields. In total we distinguished 11 categories,

including fallow, sparse and dense vegetation. Due to the high number of cloudy days, additional information was needed to improve the quality of the categorised fields. We therefore developed an event detection algorithm to detect potential turning events. Before the event detection, the time series curves are interpolated for missing values due to cloud or snow cover. We used a moving window of 15 days given the number of cloud/snow cover during winter months. The event detection algorithm works by analysing two time series curves that are expected to cross when an event occurs. For example, a sharp decrease in the barren land curve when there is new vegetation growth, crosses the steep increase in the vegetation curve. The algorithm identifies the crossing date as the turning event date. A turning event can indicate whether the field has been re-cultivated in the autumn after harvest. This allowed further refinement of the field categorisation. The results were validated using high resolution Planet Scope data. In the final step we integrated expert knowledge to estimate if the field had a cover crop or could be used for planting a cover crop, which could be used as biomass for biogas production.

In the study areas, the proportion of fields with mostly bare soil during winter varies by region, though it has remained relatively stable over time, with the notable exception of Südburgenland. In this region, more than 40% of fields were bare in winter 2018, followed by a sharp decrease to approximately 5% in both 2020 and 2022, and increase up to 30% in other years. The Mostviertel region consistently showed the highest percentage of bare fields in winter, ranging from 40% to 45%, while the Innviertel region had the lowest, with about 7% to 20%.

Our analysis suggests that the potential for cover crops is highest in the Mostviertel, where over 50% of fields could support cover crops. In contrast, the Innviertel offers a lower potential, with only about 25%–30% of fields suitable for cover crops. In Südburgenland, cover crop potential fluctuates, mirroring the variability in the proportion of bare fields during winter.

In the future this approach can be used to further analyse vegetation patterns in winter and the possible impact of climate change on agricultural practices.